

Key Action: Cooperation for innovation and the exchange of good practices
Action Type: Strategic Partnerships for youth

Project Title

Believe in Europe: Supporting the creation of a new European citizenry among the new generations

Project Coordinator

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Project Information

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EC Contribution 88,610 EUR
Partners BIDERBOST BOSCAN & ROCHIN SL (ES) , H.R.Y.O HUMAN RIGHTS YOUTH ORGANIZATION (IT) , Association de soutien de la Fondation des Femmes (FR) , ROSTO SOLIDARIO - ASSOCIACAO DE DESENVOLVIMENTO SOCIAL E HUMANO (PT)
Topics ICT - new technologies - digital competences ; Research and innovation ; EU Citizenship, EU awareness and Democracy

Project Summary

Background

The partners requested this project because they detected, after the economic crisis and Brexit, a great deficit of knowledge and skills about the EU among young people. A worrying situation due to the increasing feeling of Euroscepticism that seemed to be growing among European citizens (in general) and among the youngest (in particular).

Based on the above, the partners decided to create this project, "Believe in Europe", to develop a gamification and non-formal education methodology, both offline and online, for young people to acquire knowledge about the EU, enhance their European citizenship and increase their civic-political participation.

Objectives

GENERAL OBJECTIVE

To generate knowledge about the EU (in general) and about the following institutions (in particular): European Commission, European Parliament, European Central Bank, European Ombudsman and European Economic and Social Committee.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

To generate a process of co-creation between the partners' staff and the youth workers and young beneficiaries. The aim was to identify the points that the three groups shared in relation to the following areas: (a) how to learn EU-related content through gamification; (b) how to enhance their European citizenship; and (c) how to increase their civic-political protagonism.

Design a "Game Pack" (both offline and online versions) to learn about the EU (in general) and five of its institutions (in particular): European Commission, European Parliament, European Central Bank, European Ombudsman and European Economic and Social Committee.

To increase the beneficiaries' (partner staff, youth workers and young people) sense of belonging to the EU, as well as their knowledge about the five European institutions and their motivation to be part of an Erasmus+ project again.

Implementation

A survey was launched and focus groups were held to allow young people and workers to express their interests, issues and proposals in relation to: knowledge about the EU, its institutions, the opportunities it offers, European citizenship and civic-political participation (participation in elections and being an active agent in their community).

The 1st version of the "Believe in Europe Games Pack" was designed. A transnational face-to-face training was held to test this 1st version. At the same time, this training helped the participants to acquire the knowledge foreseen by the project.

The 2nd version of the "Believe in Europe Game Pack" was designed. Each partner held a local testing event for youth workers and young people to test updates to the game pack and finalise the design of the final version.

A multiplier event was held to disseminate the intellectual results to institutions, actors, teachers, youth workers

and young people (both beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries). The results and testimonials were shared and the "Believe in Europe Games Pack" was put into practice to re-discover the EU.

Achievements

The concrete and tangible results of the project were the following:

"Believe in Europe Games Pack" instruction manual (and its facilitation in offline mode).

European Commission Digital Escape Room

European Parliament Digital Escape Room

European Central Bank Digital Escape Room

European Ombudsman's digital Escape Room

European Economic and Social Committee's digital escape room.

On the other hand, it is also worth noting that the project succeeded in increasing the participants' sense of belonging to the EU, as well as their knowledge about the five European institutions and their motivation to be part of an Erasmus+ project again. The results obtained in the before-after evaluation were as follows:

Feeling of belonging to the EU: 3,20 / 3,64

Knowledge about European Commission: 2,47 / 3,36

Knowledge of the European Parliament: 2,07 / 3,14

Knowledge of the European Central Bank: 1,87 / 3,36

Knowledge of the European Ombudsman: 1,87 / 3,43

Knowledge of the European Economic and Social Committee: 1,80 / 3,43

I would participate in Erasmus+ again: 92% said yes.

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